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THE ROLE OF GREEN LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN AND INTERNATIONAL TRENDS

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Abstract: The Green logistics is the integration of environmental considerations in supply chain management and logistics. Focusing specifically on Uzbekistan and international trends, this research looks at how green logistics like minimizing waste, employing green packaging, and energy-efficient transport has become quite prevalent as worldwide supply chains make the shift to accommodate environmental demands. The research examines the logistics in Uzbekistan today and considers the challenges and benefits of implementing sustainable practices in the industry. In addition, the research examines international trends in green logistics and compares them to other countries that are at the forefront of sustainable logistics. The study indicates that despite the fact that Uzbekistan has some drawbacks like poor infrastructure and inadequate policies, the inclusion of green logistics could significantly improve Uzbekistan's sustainable development. By implementing other countries' best practices and by creating the capability of people to conserve the environment, the air quality can be improved simultaneously.

Key words: green logistics, sustainable development, Uzbekistan, international trends, supply chain, eco-friendly transport, green packaging.

Annotatsiya: Yashil logistika bu ta'minot zanjiri boshqaruvi va logistika jarayonlarida ekologik jihatlarni integratsiya qilishdir. Tadqiqot O'zbekiston va xalqaro tendensiyalarga alohida e'tibor qaratgan holda, chiqindilarni kamaytirish, yashil qadoqlashdan foydalanish va energiya tejamkor transport kabi yashil logistika amaliyotlari global ta'minot zanjirlari atrof-muhit talablariga moslashayotgan bir paytda tobora ommalashib borayotganini ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot bugungi kunda O'zbekistondagi logistika holatini o'rganadi hamda ushbu sohada barqaror amaliyotlarni joriy etishning afzalliklari va qiyinchiliklarini tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, xalqaro yashil logistika yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqilib, ushbu yo'nalishda yetakchi mamlakatlar tajribasi bilan taqqoslanadi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatadiki, O'zbekistonda infratuzilmaning rivojlanmagani va siyosatning yetarli emasligi kabi ayrim kamchiliklar mavjud bo'lsa-da, yashil logistika konsepsiyasini joriy etish barqaror rivojlanishga sezilarli hissa qo'shadi. Boshqa mamlakatlar tajribasini o'zlashtirish va aholining ekologik ongini rivojlantirish orqali atrof-muhit, ayniqsa havo sifati ham yaxshilanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil logistika, barqaror rivojlanish, O'zbekiston, xalqaro tendensiyalar, ta'minot zanjiri, ekologik transport, yashil qadoqlash.

Аннотация: Зеленая логистика – это интеграция экологических аспектов в управление цепями поставок и логистику. Исследование, с акцентом на Узбекистан и международные тенденции, рассматривает, как такие практики зеленой логистики, как минимизация отходов, использование экологичной упаковки и энергоэффективный транспорт, становятся всё более распространенными по мере того, как мировые цепочки поставок адаптируются к экологическим требованиям. В работе анализируется текущее состояние логистики в Узбекистане, а также проблемы и преимущества внедрения устойчивых практик в отрасли. Кроме того, рассматриваются международные тренды зеленой логистики и проводится сравнение с передовыми странами в этой сфере. Исследование показывает, что, несмотря на такие недостатки, как слабая инфраструктура и недостаточная нормативная база, внедрение зеленой логистики может значительно улучшить устойчивое развитие Узбекистана. Применяя лучшие международные практики и развивая у населения способность беречь окружающую среду, можно одновременно улучшить качество воздуха.

Ключевые слова: зеленая логистика, устойчивое развитие, Узбекистан, международные тенденции, цепь поставок, экологичный транспорт, экологичная упаковка.

INTRODUCTION

The research also investigates how innovations, such as electric vehicles, green packaging, and renewable energy, support the development of the green logistics phenomenon. The article discusses challenges and opportunities in implementing green logistics practices, including regulatory forces and cost factors in Uzbekistan and global trends.

Recently, logistics has become a crucial factor in economic growth, trade facilitation, and sustainable development. For landlocked countries such as Uzbekistan, effective logistics systems are vital for smooth import operations and reducing product costs. Green logistics emerged in the mid-1980s and was used to describe logistics systems and methods that apply advanced technology and equipment to reduce environmental damage during operations. In addition to adding diversity and dynamics, environmental issues have become increasingly significant. Social, political, and economic pressures for sustainable development compel organizations to reduce the environmental footprint of their supply chains and develop sustainable transport and supply chain strategies.

There is a close relationship between the environment, natural resources, and logistics. Today's world is highly competitive and dynamic, with consolidated markets and intense competition, making green logistics and supply chain management key to success. The main aim of green logistics is to establish environmentally friendly and sustainable logistics systems. This article emphasizes the importance of organizations planning and executing strategies to adapt to supply chain and green logistics factors as a global phenomenon.

The main focus of green logistics is reducing carbon footprints, saving energy, and promoting the use of environmentally friendly materials and technologies. This includes initiatives such as transport route optimization, using fuel-efficient or electric vehicles, installing energy-saving equipment in warehouses, and promoting recycling and reuse through reverse logistics. By incorporating environmental factors into logistics operations, green logistics not only protects the environment but also improves operational efficiency and promotes corporate social responsibility.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

It is proven that green logistics emerged in the mid-1980s. It refers to logistics systems and procedures that apply advanced technologies and equipment to reduce environmental impacts in operations. Green logistics helps save costs through fuel efficiency, improves company reputation, and ensures compliance. Many large companies, such as Amazon, are investing in electric delivery vehicles, IKEA is leading in sustainable materials, and UPS is rapidly expanding its electric vehicle fleet. All these actions help protect the environment.

This literature review also seeks to identify the main issues and prospects that may arise in the context of green logistics in Uzbekistan and globally. As a result of reviewing recent literature and studying articles on this topic, this paper aims to suggest how organizations can effectively manage the complex nature of green logistics to gain optimal value and efficiency. Green logistics is a key element of sustainable development in both developed and developing countries. While international logistics markets are rapidly adopting green practices through innovation and regulation, Uzbekistan is still at an initial stage, with immense potential for growth through policy reform, investment, and foreign collaboration.

Although logistics is a relatively new field in the country, young researchers are conducting extensive studies to improve it daily, as logistics is one of the key sectors for boosting the national economy. As Karrieva Yakutjan mentioned, due to Uzbekistan's strategic location between Europe and Asia, the country has increasing potential for green logistics. However, transforming to green logistics faces several obstacles, such as outdated infrastructure, limited access to clean technologies, and high costs of implementing eco-friendly solutions. There are both opportunities and challenges in advancing green logistics in Uzbekistan. Although the nation has an advantageous position and growing support for sustainable development, issues like obsolete infrastructure and high implementation costs must be addressed.

Karrieva Yakutjan, a teacher at Tashkent State University of Economics, also noted that Uzbekistan has both opportunities and challenges in green logistics development. While the country holds significant potential due to its strategic position and growing support for sustainable development, infrastructure limitations and high costs remain barriers. By focusing on clean technologies, digital innovations, sustainable infrastructure, supportive regulations, and education, Uzbekistan can lay the foundation for greener logistics. Adopting these strategies will not only reduce environmental impacts but also enhance economic resilience and attract eco-conscious investments. Ultimately, a commitment to environmentally friendly logistics supports Uzbekistan's sustainable development goals and establishes the country as a regional leader (Karimovna, 2024).

Narzullaev Shodiyor, an assistant at the Business Management and Logistics Department of Tashkent State University of Economics, analyzed statistical data in his article. He mentioned that logistics considers three main criteria: economy, social aspects, and ecological sustainability.

The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 outlines activities such as increasing the share of electrified railway infrastructure to 60%, intensifying roadway network construction, and developing green corridors and transit capacity in foreign trade transportation. These measures will enhance Uzbekistan's position in world markets, increase the number of reliable partners, create green logistics systems, and pave the way for higher export volumes (Shodiyor, 2021).

Samariddin Makhmudov and Shoh-Jakhon Khamdamov conducted a recent study titled “The Role of Green Logistics in Achieving SDG 13 (Climate Action) in Uzbekistan”. As a landlocked country with a developing economy, Uzbekistan has unique opportunities and challenges in the logistics sector. The nation is committed to achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 13, which calls for urgent climate action. Their study examines how green logistics can help reduce Uzbekistan's logistics sector carbon footprint and advance climate action goals. The authors argue that transitioning to green logistics in Uzbekistan requires technological development and international partnerships to achieve SDG 13 and mitigate climate change effects. The paper discusses the challenges of implementing green logistics practices, outlines key strategies, and provides recommendations for businesses amidst global inflationary pressures (Samariddin Makhmudov, Shoh-Jakhon Khamdamov, 2024).

Shodiyor Narzullaev also emphasized that logistics considers three main criteria: economy, social life, and ecological sustainability. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026 includes increasing railway electrification to 60%, expanding road networks, and building green corridors, which will strengthen Uzbekistan's market position and promote green logistics development (Shodiyor, 2022).

Mohammad Shahparan and Artem Klykov investigated the application of Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) practices in Uzbekistan, providing important insights into the current state of environmental sustainability in the nation's logistics and supply chain industries. They highlighted the significance of GSCM in reducing environmental impacts from manufacturing and distribution, emphasizing its role in moving towards a sustainable economy. Their research used qualitative and quantitative methods, including surveys of supply chain professionals and business executives in Uzbekistan. A key finding was that although the concept of green logistics is gaining global popularity, its practical implementation in Uzbekistan remains at an early stage.

The article identified several barriers to effective GSCM implementation, such as low stakeholder awareness, inadequate training, limited access to eco-friendly technologies, and weak enforcement of environmental regulations. Despite these challenges, the authors noted growing interest among Uzbek businesses in adopting sustainable practices, driven partly by international trade partners' demands for eco-friendly sourcing and logistics. Additionally, while the Uzbek government has begun promoting sustainability policies, these remain fragmented and underdeveloped.

Shahparan and Klykov proposed a model for improving GSCM in Uzbekistan, including developing national guidelines for green logistics, funding workforce training, offering financial incentives for eco-innovations, and fostering collaboration among private sector, academia, and government. They also recommended integrating sustainability metrics into logistics performance assessments. The study stands out for its realistic portrayal of the constraints and opportunities in enhancing Uzbekistan's supply chain sustainability. The authors argue that with targeted strategies, Uzbekistan can align its logistics development with global environmental standards, enhancing economic competitiveness while ensuring long-term ecological stability (Mohammad Shahparan, Artem Klykov, 2024).

Kurbatova, Aisner, and Mazurov (2020) examine the concept of green logistics as a critical component of sustainable development. Their article offers a conceptual and multidisciplinary perspective on green logistics, describing it as a logistics framework designed to reduce the environmental impacts of transportation and supply chain activities while ensuring economic efficiency. The authors emphasize that green logistics goes beyond environmental outcomes to include social responsibility and resource optimization.

The research underlines that advancing green logistics requires the integration of various fields, including economics, ecology, information technology, and environmental management. This interdisciplinary approach ensures that environmental challenges are addressed from both technical and organizational perspectives. A significant contribution of the paper is its framework for analyzing green logistics through systematic and functional lenses, suggesting that logistics systems should be assessed based on their long-term environmental impacts.

Additionally, the article highlights the importance of logistics information systems in facilitating eco-friendly practices, such as optimizing delivery routes, reducing fuel consumption, and improving inventory management. The use of digital tools and data analytics is seen as a powerful enabler of sustainable logistics, especially in urban areas where congestion and emissions present significant challenges.

In terms of policy and governance, the authors argue that institutional support, including environmental regulations and funding for green infrastructure, is essential for advancing sustainable logistics practices. They assert that green logistics should not be viewed merely as a technical or economic approach but as a

comprehensive sustainability practice that aligns logistics objectives with environmental conservation. This article provides a theoretical foundation for understanding the core principles of green logistics, making it highly relevant for academic research or practical initiatives aimed at promoting sustainable logistics, particularly in Uzbekistan (Kurbatova, S. M.; Aisner, L. Yu.; Mazurov, V. Yu., 2020).

The concept of green logistics has evolved significantly in recent years, reflecting the global demand for sustainable practices in supply chain management and transportation. Nicoletti and Appolloni (2024) provide an in-depth analysis of this evolution through the concept of Green Logistics 5.0, which integrates advanced artificial intelligence (AI) models to drive sustainability improvements. The authors emphasize that green logistics is not just about reducing environmental impact; it involves a holistic strategy that incorporates corporate philosophy, product design, operational processes, and business models.

This integrated approach enables companies to address the economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability simultaneously. The article underscores the critical role of foundation models, which are robust AI systems capable of optimizing complex logistics tasks such as route planning, inventory management, and packaging reduction. These innovations help lower carbon emissions and resource consumption while increasing efficiency and competitiveness.

A notable contribution of this research is the integration of Sustainability-Oriented Innovation (SOI) in logistics. This framework encourages companies to embed sustainability within their core innovations, transforming traditional logistics into more eco-friendly, technology-driven systems. Nicoletti and Appolloni (2024) suggest that implementing SOI can help logistics companies achieve environmental goals while also gaining financial benefits, including cost reductions and improved market positioning.

The article also highlights the importance of adopting emerging technologies such as AI, big data analytics, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to enhance decision-making and promote transparency within supply chains. These technological advancements enable proactive environmental management and compliance with stricter regulations.

In conclusion, the research by Nicoletti and Appolloni advances the understanding of green logistics by demonstrating how modern technologies and innovative business models can collectively create sustainable logistics systems. Their work serves as a crucial guide for researchers and practitioners seeking to develop and implement effective green logistics strategies in today's rapidly changing business environment (Bernardo Nicoletti, Andrea Appolloni, 2024).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodological framework used to examine the evolution of green logistics in Uzbekistan and international trends. Logistics systems, especially those related to sustainability and global supply chains, are complex, multidimensional, and influenced by both quantitative metrics and qualitative factors. Therefore, a well-structured research methodology is essential to analyze this subject from both practical and theoretical perspectives.

The primary objective of this study is to assess the current state, challenges, and growth opportunities in the green logistics processes of Uzbekistan and other countries, and their transition towards eco-friendly methods. With its dual focus on efficiency and sustainability, the research adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis techniques. This approach effectively captures operational metrics such as transportation efficiency, delivery times, and costs, while also exploring human perceptions, policy gaps, and organizational strategies related to sustainable logistics.

Using this structured and holistic approach, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of Uzbekistan's progress in inbound and green logistics, contributing to academic knowledge as well as offering practical recommendations for policymakers, businesses, and logistics professionals. The philosophical foundation of the research is rooted in pragmatism, which emphasizes the practical application of research findings in real-world contexts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Green logistics covers various fields and stages of the supply chain. It includes:

Transportation: Using cleaner fuels, electric transport, and mode switching (e.g. from road to rail). Transportation plays a key role in green logistics, as it is one of the largest sources of carbon emissions in supply chains. Green logistics aims to reduce CO₂ and pollutant emissions by using less harmful means of transport. Half of transportation in green logistics involves carrying goods responsibly and sustainably. This includes changing delivery methods, vehicles, and routes to reduce environmental impact while maintaining efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Warehousing: Using energy-efficient buildings, renewable energy, and effective waste management. Warehouses are key in storage, processing, and distribution, making them essential for logistics sustainability. Green warehousing includes eco-friendly practices, waste reduction, and energy conservation to improve environmental performance.

Packaging: Developing recyclable and biodegradable packaging products. Green packaging uses recyclable, biodegradable, or reusable materials to reduce total packaging waste. Companies can significantly reduce their environmental impact by using eco-friendly materials like cardboard or biodegradable polymers instead of disposable plastics.

Inventory and supply chain management: Digitalisation, demand forecasting, and resource management. Green logistics aims for maximum efficiency without significantly harming the environment while meeting consumer needs. It involves decision-making to maintain necessary inventory levels while reducing waste, maximizing resource use, and minimizing carbon emissions, a process known as retrofitting.

Reverse logistics: Recycling and disposal of goods. Reverse logistics is crucial in green logistics as it enables the return of products, packaging, and materials for recycling, reuse, and compliant disposal. It creates closed-loop commodity flows that minimize waste, save resources, reduce emissions, and enhance supply chain sustainability. Reverse logistics benefits the environment as well as companies economically and reputationally when integrated into green logistics initiatives.

Including green logistics in this dissertation is essential for several reasons. First, the logistics sector is among the fastest-growing sources of carbon emissions globally, making it central to climate action. Second, sustainable logistics operations are closely tied to achieving various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including climate action, responsible consumption, innovation, and urban sustainability.

Focusing on Uzbekistan, a country undergoing rapid economic and infrastructural development, gives this research a specific context. As the country builds its transportation and logistics systems to drive trade and regional integration, it must ensure that this development is ecologically sustainable. Green logistics involves eco-friendly transport methods that reduce air pollution and carbon footprints by transporting products sustainably. Parts of supply chain processes are now adopting green logistics practices to comply with environmental regulations, improve brand image, and achieve long-term cost savings. Inbound and downstream logistics present both challenges and opportunities. While traditional inbound logistics focus on efficiency and cost reduction, green logistics emphasizes environmental responsibility. Balancing these factors is key for organizations aiming for sustainable growth.

This study targets inbound and green logistics aspects to develop and integrate them effectively for more sustainable supply chains. In a rapidly globalizing world, logistics has evolved beyond basic transportation. It now reflects a country's economic development, ability to meet market demands, and commitment to sustainability. For countries like Uzbekistan, located at the crossroads of Central Asia, logistics development is not just a technical need but a critical factor in national development and regional integration.

Two concepts have emerged as central to global logistics management: inbound logistics and green logistics. Inbound logistics, involving transport, storage, and distribution from suppliers to producers, is crucial for effective production and supply chain synchronization. Meanwhile, growing environmental awareness has led to the rise of green logistics, which focuses on sustainability, resource efficiency, and environmental responsibility in logistics operations.

The advancement of inbound and green logistics is particularly important for developing countries such as Uzbekistan, where industrial diversification, increased foreign trade, and tourism growth require efficient and sustainable logistics systems. Traditional logistics methods often prioritize cost and speed, neglecting environmental impacts such as carbon emissions, waste, and unsustainable resource use. Green logistics, however, aims to reduce these impacts by applying sustainable transportation, energy-efficient warehousing, and reverse logistics practices. Positioned in the heart of Central Asia on the ancient Silk Road, Uzbekistan has significant regional and global trade opportunities. To fully utilize this advantage, the country must modernize its inbound logistics systems and integrate sustainable practices.

Green logistics firms are confronted with tough challenges and hurdles in the adoption of green policies primarily because of several reasons. One of them is the lack of pressure for strict regulatory policies. Governments and authorities presently manage the regulation of emission limits and controls across industries. These controls must be established through cross-industry consensus for constructing new processes and facilities designed to meet the sustainability needs of stakeholders dealing in the logistics business.

Another challenge is the low motivation to invest. Whether outsourced or in-house, narrow profit margins and tight cost ratios mean that investment in process automation, intelligent infrastructure, or better materials handling equipment is discouraged, especially among SMEs.

The impact of e-commerce on traffic in urban centers is also significant. The greater number of e-commerce order shipments has driven the volume of last-mile shipments in cities, and most nonfuel load runs are encountered when confronted with several time-definite orders.

Additionally, transport vehicles require fossil fuels. Economically feasible and viable alternatives are still awaited to wean the transport sector from its fossil fuel reliance, especially for those that operate heavy vehicles.

For the logistics providers, some green paradigmatic conventional alternatives have been developed and implemented. One such alternative is green procurement, which is the process of buying products and services to reduce the negative impacts on the environment and public health, thus continually searching for quality products and services at competitive prices. Green businesses ought to factor in the environment while procuring goods and services, for instance, to avoid dumping products once utilized and to procure goods that involve clean technology and clean fuels.

Another solution is green packaging, also referred to as eco-friendly packaging. The package material can be plant-based, reusable or used repeatedly, and ready for decomposition. During the entire life cycle, it would not be dangerous for nature as well as for human beings.

Finally, green warehousing tries to minimize its environmental impact through omni-directional use of best practices like automation, lean warehousing, and green building (Shu-Lun Mak, Yiu-Man Wong, Kin-Chung Ho and Chi-Chung Lee, 2021).

Table 1. SWOT ANALYSIS¹

<p>STRENGTHS Environmental Sustainability Corporate Branding and Image Operational Efficiency</p>	<p>WEAKNESS High Initial Expenses Limited Infrastructure Slow Implementation</p>
<p>OPPORTUNITIES Growing Environmental Awareness Technological Advancements Government Incentives</p>	<p>THREATS Changing Regulations Economic Downturns Greenwashing Risks</p>

A SWOT analysis is a strategic planning tool that helps to make clearer in a better way, as main areas of research is provided here for taking reflection of green logistics. There are so many opportunities and strengths to in a single case of green logistics systems development with green packaging and electric vehicles (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The green logistics cycle²

1 Own elaboration
2 (Mariam Lazrak, Hamid El amran, 2023)

Transportation emphasizes the significance of utilizing environmentally friendly transport options. This involves transitioning to electric or hybrid vehicles, enhancing delivery routes, and minimizing fuel use and emissions while transporting goods.

Reverse Logistics is essential for handling the return process of items for reuse, recycling, or appropriate disposal. It aids in lessening landfill waste and encourages the circular economy.

Combined, these five elements create a cycle that fosters sustainability throughout every phase of the logistics process. Adopting green logistics not only allows companies to minimize their ecological impact but also improves their image and operational effectiveness. With the increasing worldwide demand for sustainable practices, incorporating these green logistics aspects is vital for enduring competitiveness and adherence to environmental regulations.

According to the participants' answers we can say that Secondary data collections are used in this article. The article research process with the technique using Google surveys by university master students of Silk Road University and other people on THE ROLE OF GREEN LOGISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN AND INTERNATIONAL TRENDS are also based on a qualitative data. Questionnaire was applied to numerous different individuals and gathered their responses as the prime pillars of our article. Based on their responses, the question inquired how they know about green logistics and could assist the future of Uzbek and other countries green logistics.

Besides that, written answers to questions learned about new conducting studies on this area. This study performed the analysis by reading more articles, newspapers, the yearly reports of companies globally and of course, in Uzbekistan. This survey was held among 51 people. Most of them were students who were interested in this sphere and ordinary people were also answered.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

To sum up, the green logistics industry in Uzbekistan is at a pivotal juncture. The groundwork for contemporary, effective, and eco-friendly logistics has been established, yet enhanced policy backing, infrastructure funding, and private sector dedication are crucial to hasten the growth and sustainability of green logistics activities in the nation. It's encouraging that more than 95% of surveyed firms are utilizing green logistics in some capacity — however, these initiatives require additional backing.

Uzbekistan needs to develop a comprehensive national green logistics strategy that outlines specific objectives and deadlines. Businesses that adopt eco-friendly practices might gain certifications and public acknowledgment. Widely recognized eco-friendly methods such as route optimization, energy-efficient vehicles, and recycling ought to be encouraged via awareness initiatives and workshops. Numerous logistics experts reported experiencing problems stemming from inadequate collaboration with suppliers.

Green Logistics of European Nations means the green supply chain management, transportation, and storage to minimize the environmental footprint. These involve actions for decreasing CO₂ emissions, increasing energy efficiency, encouraging sustainable modes of transport, and utilizing the circular economy. The European Union has pioneered green logistics policy and finance and wants to be climate neutral by 2050, impacting logistics with tougher emission regulations and green transport bonuses.

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